

Liver tissue transcriptome data analysis for identification of key miRNAs and genes in sheep (*Ovis Aries*) with different diets

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Abstract

The development of bioinformatics and data science has improved the ability to analyze numerous biological data types. Moreover, Next Generation Sequencing enables scientists to rapidly measure the expression of various genes. Besides that, livestock breeding is focused on creating animals with better productivity, which requires a thorough understanding of what genes or gene regulators participate in different metabolism. Therefore, this study used Illumina-sequence transcriptome data of *Ovis Aries* livers with a specific diet to identify the expression of important miRNAs and genes in different metabolism. Gene expression analysis was performed, and the result identified 15916 differentially expressed genes (DEGs), including 5870 DEGs in the high energy group, 2259 DEGs in the light grazing group, 4141 DEGs in the over- grazing group, and 3646 DEGs in the oil supplement group. In addition, this study demonstrates the existence of 14 different miRNA and their association with the highlighted genes. Moreover, the role of mir143 and mir125b has been discussed, and the results successfully validate their association with Hexokinase 2 in glucose metabolism.

Key words: Metabolism, MiRNA, *Ovis Aries*, Liver, Transcriptome

Introduction

Sheep are one of the earliest animals domesticated by humans (Mazinani & Rude, 2020). It is considered a valuable animal in food industries and has a great potential for usage in lactation (Gibson, 1991). Due to the importance of sheep in animal husbandry, several studies worked on the most valuable strain using a variety of criteria (Vera et al.). For instance, Fonseca et al. has shown that feed efficiency is an important factor and criterion used in genomic selection (Fonseca et al., 2019). This study categorized the sheep into different strains based on feed efficiency and compared the genomic sequences of these strains to detect any contrasts which could be helpful in genomic selection. Metabolism action and feed efficiency are highly connected to liver function.

Improper liver activities decrease feed efficiency. Therefore, studying the metabolic pathways and regulatory mechanisms of liver cells could be useful to have a comprehensive view of them.

The liver is one of the most vital organs in the metabolism process. It plays a significant role in regulating blood glucose, lipid, and protein metabolism (Han et al., 2016). Several intracellular regulators control the liver's activities. According to the regulatory role of Micro-RNA, this study demonstrates the expression of these regulators in different conditions.

Micro-RNA (miRNA) is a class of Snc-RNAs (Small non-coding RNA) with regulatory function in the cellular system. MiRNAs can be expressed during cancer (Chen et al., 2012) or may express in different cellular processes such as lipid (Fernández-Hernando et al., 2011) or protein metabolism (Lee et al., 2016). Even though several studies have demonstrated the significant functions of miRNAs in controlling various metabolic pathways, there are still unidentified regulatory miRNAs. Therefore, this study analyzes the transcriptome of liver cells based on the different diets to identify significant expression of regulators and genes in various metabolisms.

Materials and methods

Samples collection: A total of 12 samples with 4 categories of diets have been collected from NCBI databanks. Table one show the characterization and accession number of each sample.

Table 1. Samples information with accession number. LG for light-grazing, OG for overgrazing, HE for high energy, HO for high oil.

Group name	Diet	Number of samples	Accession number
LG	Light grazing	2	SRR7231991 SRR7231992
OG	Overgrazing	2	SRR7231994 SRR7231993
HE	High amount of energy in short time	3	SRR7446897 SRR7446899 SRR7446902
HO	High amount of oil supplements	3	SRR6716250 SRR6716251 SRR6716252
Control	Normal	2	SRR13496247 SRR13496256

Bioinformatics analysis: In the first step, Illumina-sequences transcriptome was downloaded from the NCBI data bank and quality assessment was performed by the Fast QC program. All the sequences were aligned to the Ovis Aries reference genome from the Ensemble data bank (Oar_v3.1.GCA_000298735.1) using STAR toolkits (Dobin et al., 2012) and Finally, the expression level of genes was determined using Future count (Liao et al., 2014). In the second step, all the data are listed and arranged in the R program. Moreover, P-values were adjusted using the Benjamin and Hochberg method for controlling the false discovery rate (Tripathi et al., 2022). According to Hu & Zou (2021), genes with log2 fold change values greater than 1 or less than -1 extracted with python and are considered differentially expressed genes. The top 1% of genes are identified based on the log2 fold change and are regarded to be significant genes in different metabolism. Data was finally imported into the Mat Lab program to generate the bar plot. Additionally, volcano plots are generated based on the P-value to highlight the significantly expressed genes.

Result

The transcriptome analysis demonstrates the expression of 15916 genes in all groups. At first, the miRNAs and gene expression results examine separately and their relationship was discussed at the end.

MiRNA expression analysis: The analysis identified the expression of 14 different miRNAs. 8 miRNAs were expressed in all four diets while 6 miRNAs are only expressed in a specific diet. (figure.1). This may demonstrate that these 6 miRNAs probably play a significant role in a unique metabolism pathway. However, the reset may not participate in any metabolism action.

(A)

(B)

Figure .1 List of expressed miRNAs. The colors show the diet, the x axe shows the name of miRNA and the Y axe shows log2. (A) 6 miRNA which is observed in specific diets. (B) 8 miRNA which observed in all diets

The result also showed that several miRNAs, including mir26A and mir199, were down-regulated, especially in the HE diet. In contrast, mir23A and mir29B are presented only in high-energy groups, which upregulated significantly. Due to the high amount of glucose in the HE diet, these miRNAs are most likely related to glucose metabolism. Additionally, the over-expression of mir221 in the overgrazing group may demonstrate the importance of this miRNA in regulating nutrient intake. To conclude, some of these miRNAs regulate cellular metabolism. Also, it has been understood that some of them participate in the immunity process, which will explain later. All of these findings reveal the role of miRNAs in regulating metabolism. These miRNAs will enhance different genes and control their expression, thus transcriptome expression analysis has been performed to identify the influenced genes by these miRNAs.

Gene expression analysis of liver: The gene expression results revealed 5870 DEGs in the high energy group, 2259 DEGs in the light grazing group, 4141 DEGs in the overgrazing group, and 3646 DEGs in the oil supplement group. According to the number of expressed

genes, the top one percent of expressed genes are considered keygens. As a result, 115 candidate genes have been selected based on the log₂ fold change, which is present in Table

According to the Gene Card data bank reports 70.4% of these genes are protein-coding and contribute to different metabolism. Also, a few of them are related to the immune system, especially in high-energy samples. Moreover, the volcano plots have been generated to illustrate the expressed genes in each group by considering P-value beside the Log₂ fold change (Figure.2).

The volcano plot demonstrates the significant expression of several genes in each diet. It shows that ENS4383, ENS0538, ENS4157, ENS6854, and ENS6123 are up-regulated in all diets, in contrast, ENS5270 and ENS0891 are down-regulated. As a result, these genes most likely are not related to any particular metabolic process because the expression changes were similar. However, EN0034 was down-regulated only in HE and HO diets, and EN0334 was up-regulated in OG and LG diets, which means they could be important and will be examined in the following.

Figure.2 This figure shows the volcano plots for each diet and Important genes were marked. Green colors show the genes which up-regulated, red colors show the genes which down-regulated and the blue colors show the genes with no differential expression.

Discussion

In order to have a better understanding of metabolic processes, the performance of highly expressed genes and miRNAs is briefly examined in the following.

Mir30 is one of the regulatory miRNAs in lipid metabolism. The importance of Mir30 in lipid metabolism is vividly shown in the volcano plots. Several studies assert that up-regulation of Mir30 will reduce lipid production and

prevent hyperlipidemia (Zaragosi et al., 2011),(Veitch et al., 2022). According to this assertion, the expression of Mir30 is expected to be higher on the oil diet compared to other ones because, on this diet, cells already contain a large amount of oil and do not need to produce more. The bar plot shows that Mir30 expression was higher in the oil diet than in the other diets, which supports this claim.

Mir143 is another regulatory miRNA. Certain studies demonstrate the function of miRNAs 143 and 29 in glucose metabolism (Zhao et al., 2016). or instance, Sun & Zhang claim that the up-regulation of mirna143 would influence the hk2 gene. As a result, the cell uptake more glucose to produce different products (Sun & Zhang, 2017). According to our result, the expression level of mir143 in the HE sample was lower than in others, which resulted in a down-regulation of HK2 genes and reduced glucose uptake. This action is not only beneficial to balancing the amount of glucose in the cell but also prevents the cell from cancer by reducing energy production and inhibiting cell mitosis. Moreover, HK2 may be under-expressed due to the influence of other regulatory factors, such as immunity miRNAs. Recently, numerous studies demonstrate that some miRNAs, such as mir16b, mir30b, and 199a, have a significant function in immune systems (Wang et al., 2019). These miRNAs are effective in preventing cancer by controlling energy production. Our findings can confirm this fact because the expression of these miRNAs seems to be related to the amount of glucose intake and energy production.

ENS0034 is another gene that is down-regulated in the HE and OG group. This gene is called CYTB which is a protein-coding gene for cytochrome b. Cytochrome b is one of the 11 parts of a group of proteins known as complex

III. This protein plays a significant role in mitochondria (Degli Esposti et al., 1993). Electrons from dehydrogenases are transported to cytochrome c by cytochrome

b. Generally, complex III plays a key role in oxidative phosphorylation which produces adenosine triphosphate (ATP) (Schöttler et al., 2015). Consequently, down-regulating of ENS0034 reduces the ATP production in HE and HO samples, which contain high energy. A few studies have demonstrated that a high

fatty acid and glucose intake reduces the production of ATP (Köhnke et al., 2007). This action leads the cell to balance the amount of ATP in the cell.

High-energy foods contain a high amount of protein and carbohydrates. Numerous studies have examined how carbohydrates affect protein synthesis, and findings indicate that a high carbohydrate intake increases protein synthesis (Figueiredo & Cameron-Smith, 2013). EN0334 is a non-coding RNA called Metazoa_SRP which is a component of the signal recognition particle (SRP). These particles connect to the ribosome and decrease protein synthesis (Walter & Blobel, 1981); As a result, down-regulating of Metazoa_SRP promotes protein synthesis. Also, it balances the energy by consuming it for this production. On the other hand, it has been mentioned that protein synthesis requires a lot of energy. Therefore, Metazia_SRP was up-regulated in the Light grazing diet because the cell does not have sufficient energy to make a high amount of protein.

In addition, some other microRNAs can control protein synthesis too. As an example, Sun et al assert that Mir125b decreases protein synthesis by inhibiting muscle stem cell differentiation (Sun et al., 2016). To conclude, it has been examined that down-regulating EN034 and mir125b, besides the presence of carbohydrates, will increase protein synthesis in a high-energy diet.

EN14 is a novel protein-coding gene for 87aa protein. Although this protein's precise function has not yet been determined, the results indicated that the expression of these genes was considerably altered by the amount of food consumed. This gene was also down-regulated in oil samples. It may play a role in fatty acid metabolism.

To summarize, the function of miRNAs in metabolism is illustrated and supported by all of these findings. Furthermore, the expression of several immune system miRNAs aids in our understanding of the importance of dietary energy intake.

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Table.2 The top one percent of gene expression based on log2FoldChange. Totally 114 genes were selected as the top one percent in gene expression based on log2 fold change. Genes sorted from positive to a negative amount of log2FoldChange.

Name	Base Mean	log2FoldChange	LfcSE	Stat	Pvalue
ENSOARG00020006805	182.699421	6.388687105	0.590783	10.813931	2.9572E-27
ENSOARG00020017612	96.4367021	6.086711866	0.5820454	10.457452	1.35E-25
ENSOARG00020020334	504.549057	5.920762151	0.3873216	15.286424	9.42E-53
ENSOARG00020020334	418.541295	5.342604837	0.3586256	14.897446	3.42E-50
ENSOARG00020021607	61.239977	5.296214655	0.6221498	8.5127649	1.7E-17
ENSOARG00020009688	43.1982242	5.188673123	0.6504583	7.9769501	1.5E-15
ENSOARG00020022223	45.4359264	5.139247769	0.6046629	8.4993599	1.9064E-17
ENSOARG00020009052	124.959944	5.052598659	0.4648654	10.86895	1.62E-27
ENSOARG00020010874	44.0799778	5.005650093	0.6343927	7.8904594	3.0108E-15
ENSOARG00020004157	1483.20843	4.976360084	0.2801006	17.766333	1.2884E-70
ENSOARG00020005812	56.974326	4.816488152	0.5942553	8.1050827	5.27E-16
ENSOARG00020006805	94.0284854	4.804717573	0.5618217	8.5520329	1.21E-17
ENSOARG00020016558	8706.12863	4.788991778	0.349411	13.705897	9.3603E-43
ENSOARG00020006805	137.910641	4.763121028	0.48942	9.7321746	2.2E-22
ENSOARG00020023033	19.019443	4.688231221	0.7329693	6.3962182	1.5927E-10
ENSOARG00020021607	60.3134884	4.659068367	0.5288575	8.8096857	1.25E-18
ENSOARG00020009052	128.024206	4.648362319	0.4307227	10.792006	3.76E-27
ENSOARG00020004038	115.773067	4.547789028	0.4823811	9.4277934	4.1881E-21
ENSOARG00020017612	62.4166052	4.54762403	0.53989	8.4232423	3.66E-17
ENSOARG00020014263	45.9493521	4.53935702	0.5752731	7.8907866	3.0029E-15
ENSOARG00020012115	121.871656	4.536729178	0.4743525	9.564046	1.1324E-21
ENSOARG00020004458	249.860479	4.518146408	0.3672902	12.301299	8.9129E-35
ENSOARG00020011295	4111.92598	4.452949021	0.362997	12.267178	1.3591E-34
ENSOARG00020010025	270.555197	4.445464543	0.3521204	12.624842	1.54E-36
ENSOARG00020004394	66.3081579	4.403079905	0.5448248	8.0816444	6.3899E-16

ENSOARG00020020907	266.482375	4.368491412	0.3354036	13.024582	8.8686E-39
ENSOARG00020009688	47.7094244	4.294301622	0.5610265	7.6543653	1.94E-14
ENSOARG00020006917	48.6611304	4.246435418	0.5589273	7.5974741	3.0197E-14
ENSOARG00020005812	56.3842096	4.21410071	0.5205356	8.0957018	5.69E-16
ENSOARG00020006701	555.982007	4.207813779	0.4227858	9.952589	2.4571E-23
ENSOARG00020004143	318.704369	4.198832722	0.4129392	10.168161	2.7505E-24
ENSOARG00020016615	29.0049794	4.163012719	0.6153037	6.7657857	1.3259E-11
ENSOARG00020013806	28.816582	4.080733443	0.6481874	6.2956078	3.06E-10
ENSOARG00020004493	487.450391	4.036029824	0.3803303	10.611906	2.6234E-26
ENSOARG00020024981	38.8243245	4.017881732	0.4516634	8.8957439	5.8029E-19
ENSOARG00020018791	2534.99818	4.016717341	0.7212544	5.5690715	2.561E-08
ENSOARG00020001145	25.3112003	4.006853978	0.4614794	8.6826277	3.8673E-18
ENSOARG00020004948	172.551784	3.986796144	0.4010285	9.9414287	2.7486E-23
ENSOARG00020011434	629.890894	3.985310515	0.4192422	9.5059865	1.9816E-21
ENSOARG00020010810	139.306374	3.982329803	0.4042763	9.8505154	6.8193E-23
ENSOARG00020020166	29.1179332	3.966390225	0.6844527	5.7949811	6.8329E-09
ENSOARG00020025404	23.5930087	3.957304807	0.7089043	5.5822836	2.37E-08
ENSOARG00020001911	45.3288885	3.935652919	0.5670934	6.940044	3.92E-12
ENSOARG00020015045	13.8920707	3.930372208	0.6528009	6.0207825	1.7358E-09
ENSOARG00020001145	92.069861	3.874175827	0.4813275	8.0489394	8.35E-16
ENSOARG00020019241	15.5862797	3.866348217	0.5708381	6.7731084	1.2604E-11
ENSOARG00020004948	227.911389	3.836927161	0.3505029	10.946919	6.87E-28
ENSOARG00020010025	211.165233	3.822882253	0.3360048	11.377465	5.42E-30
ENSOARG00020009956	130.103106	3.812662732	0.4190964	9.097341	9.26E-20
ENSOARG00020008397	678.440024	3.798487003	0.3740263	10.155667	3.1266E-24
ENSOARG00020003518	225.451045	3.774452496	0.4743987	7.9562875	1.7728E-15
ENSOARG00020017719	1127.00203	3.763275167	0.2798554	13.447212	3.197E-41
ENSOARG00020025559	2550.75296	3.760274813	0.3700881	10.160486	2.9759E-24
ENSOARG00020000054	964.286794	3.752784726	0.5408242	6.939011	3.9486E-12
ENSOARG00020021218	19.4033154	3.734448829	0.7330841	5.0941613	3.5029E-07
ENSOARG00020011316	665.831295	3.724329469	0.4390922	8.4818839	2.2158E-17

ENSOARG00020002122	7.96008655	-3.785418612	0.8135493	-4.6529676	3.2719E-06
ENSOARG00020019955	17.5457431	-3.789177654	0.6996759	-5.4156182	6.1077E-08
ENSOARG00020013837	85.668187	-3.806600568	0.3755179	-10.136936	3.7879E-24
ENSOARG00020024357	37.5433661	-3.851569115	0.586498	-6.5670631	5.1317E-11
ENSOARG00020017131	11.3604514	-3.851680116	0.7533471	-5.1127566	3.1749E-07
ENSOARG00020000022	714.90866	-3.857897158	0.812758	-4.746674	2.0679E-06
ENSOARG00020014428	10.9163431	-3.865276444	0.8204358	-4.7112482	2.462E-06
ENSOARG00020017953	19.8755245	-3.901237935	0.7526896	-5.1830634	2.1827E-07
ENSOARG00020004802	110.283815	-3.950660389	0.5183492	-7.6216198	2.51E-14
ENSOARG00020021140	15.0000844	-3.973953229	0.7731673	-5.139836	2.7498E-07
ENSOARG00020010904	12.5166666	-4.014017351	0.7452824	-5.3859012	7.2083E-08
ENSOARG00020018504	11.5191517	-4.055688909	0.8085664	-5.0159008	5.2786E-07
ENSOARG00020007106	10.3947746	-4.060429183	0.8031621	-5.0555536	4.2914E-07
ENSOARG00020003500	13.7866158	-4.098948542	0.7454967	-5.4982784	3.8352E-08
ENSOARG00020002675	403.932856	-4.099973577	0.3379919	-12.130391	7.29E-34
ENSOARG00020018857	73.7296787	-4.13440783	0.5588793	-7.3976754	1.3859E-13
ENSOARG00020014326	10.9111756	-4.197705645	0.7928473	-5.2944694	1.1936E-07
ENSOARG00020000589	11.6680022	-4.199994056	0.7969345	-5.2701873	1.3629E-07
ENSOARG00020015287	31.4376214	-4.244873294	0.6138297	-6.9153922	4.6657E-12
ENSOARG00020026159	220.229043	-4.248595388	0.3604676	-11.786344	4.5904E-32
ENSOARG00020006787	104.025792	-4.259530827	0.4784277	-8.9031861	5.4266E-19
ENSOARG00020003350	56.3135257	-4.260405387	0.5824414	-7.314737	2.58E-13
ENSOARG00020023060	45.4576913	-4.349695224	0.5522173	-7.8767821	3.36E-15
ENSOARG00020019704	91.04684	-4.357272784	0.5535962	-7.8708497	3.5224E-15
ENSOARG00020014158	472.439243	-4.363161879	0.3603338	-12.108666	9.5E-34
ENSOARG00020025718	18.7267256	-4.38045825	0.7474611	-5.8604496	4.6162E-09
ENSOARG00020004419	73.4127861	-4.404354665	0.4684242	-9.4024917	5.3286E-21
ENSOARG00020014649	23.6304975	-4.421279213	0.7047955	-6.2731374	3.5384E-10
ENSOARG00020013531	19.0374319	-4.430986673	0.8018104	-5.5262272	3.2719E-08
ENSOARG00020024777	445.493749	-4.451401969	0.7589112	-5.865511	4.4775E-09
ENSOARG00020013040	1020.57841	-4.469768857	0.309528	-14.440594	2.87E-47

ENSOARG00020004960	14.1831525	-4.493955959	0.7813178	-5.7517642	8.8317E-09
ENSOARG00020024642	50.4818267	-4.52953121	0.5143288	-8.8066844	1.289E-18
ENSOARG00020018797	14.9517976	-4.552824428	0.7789355	-5.844931	5.0678E-09
ENSOARG00020023708	446.900951	-4.5626849	0.3602104	-12.666723	9.04E-37
ENSOARG00020017621	19.2531109	-4.632719956	0.7113362	-6.5127006	7.3812E-11
ENSOARG00020024389	22.875547	-4.71440195	0.7197903	-6.549688	5.7657E-11
ENSOARG00020023060	40.704663	-4.771240658	0.6604013	-7.2247594	5.02E-13
ENSOARG00020006787	276.156466	-4.771305424	0.4849909	-9.8379267	7.73E-23
ENSOARG00020006589	101.371101	-4.852039053	0.5137155	-9.4449929	3.55E-21
ENSOARG00020000011	111.072205	-4.873003401	0.5109675	-9.5368166	1.4728E-21
ENSOARG00020024587	35.9489764	-4.906344742	0.6836258	-7.1769448	7.1287E-13
ENSOARG00020008872	305.845689	-4.942725281	0.3921744	-12.603387	2.0227E-36
ENSOARG00020008303	1524.21751	-4.992385822	0.400458	-12.466691	1.13E-35
ENSOARG00020018890	24.0355777	-5.24028423	0.7424603	-7.0579994	1.6892E-12
ENSOARG00020019836	24.4432288	-5.307061772	0.7367545	-7.2032975	5.8774E-13
ENSOARG00020014158	143.014015	-5.350675685	0.5184288	-10.320946	5.6662E-25
ENSOARG00020022689	48.5071764	-5.365708579	0.6689834	-8.0206904	1.0515E-15
ENSOARG00020003858	111.414572	-5.47005072	0.5453404	-10.030525	1.12E-23
ENSOARG00020003858	123.746597	-5.555722126	0.4955159	-11.211996	3.56E-29
ENSOARG00020016723	3095.9667	-5.667841549	0.4315997	-13.132171	2.1539E-39
ENSOARG00020008872	610.951739	-5.68131624	0.3948449	-14.388728	6.09E-47
ENSOARG00020000025	55.0222269	-5.912745159	0.7364226	-8.029011	9.8262E-16
ENSOARG00020018857	150.666626	-6.679340151	0.643875	-10.37366	3.2677E-25
ENSOARG00020000011	228.802416	-7.050008554	0.5611206	-12.564158	3.3239E-36
ENSOARG00020000034	4953.53781	-7.218603759	0.3335564	-21.641331	7.34E-104
ENSOARG00020000034	4668.16999	-8.749702506	0.3828483	-22.854228	1.327E-115
ENSOARG00020016693	2104.90303	-9.565100205	0.5737569	-16.670997	2.1301E-62